

Deliverable D12.2

Project Title:	Building data bridges between biological and medical infrastructures in Europe	
Project Acronym:	BioMedBridges	
Grant agreement no.:	284209	
	Research Infrastructures, FP7 Capacities Specific Programme; [INFRA-2011-2.3.2.] "Implementation of common solutions for a cluster of ESFRI infrastructures in the field of "Life sciences"	
Deliverable title:	Documentation from workshops 3 and 4	
WP No.	12	
Lead Beneficiary:	1: EMBL	
WP Title	Training	
Contractual delivery date:	30 June 2015	
Actual delivery date:	30 June 2015	
WP leader:	Cath Brooksbank	1: EMBL
Contributing partner(s):	1: EMBL	

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1 Executive Summary

- This deliverable summarises the third and fourth workshops run by WP12 – Training – as part of the BioMedBridges project.
- *Preparing for the data deluge*, our third knowledge exchange workshop with project partners, brought together the BMS research infrastructures with the European e-infrastructures to discuss biological data needs in the coming five years.
- Data strategies for research infrastructures, our final knowledge exchange workshop, examined how research infrastructures can develop strategies for managing biological data.
- During both workshops we used ‘living documents’, which could be simultaneously edited by all the participants, to capture information on the delegates’ needs and expectations, and to address these.
- Subsequently BioMedBridges produced reports on the activities of these workshops and plans for the future. These are available on the BioMedBridges website.

2 Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

No.	Objective	Yes	No
1	Deliver short courses to train project participants in relevant areas of bioinformatics that are outside of their current experience and necessary to build crosslinks between the data resources of the BMS RIs	Yes	
2	Produce documentation on the resources developed, for use initially within the project but ultimately by the end-users of the integrated services developed by BioMedBridges	Yes	

3	Deliver short courses enabling end-users of the biomedical research infrastructures to benefit from the developments of work packages 3–11	Yes	
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3 Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Background

This report describes the second two workshops run by WP12 – Training – within the BioMedBridges project as part of the d12.2 deliverable due for completion at the end of month 42 (June 2015). Task 1 & 2 focuses on internal training – through knowledge exchange workshops. These workshops are intended to disseminate key knowledge and skills among the project partners, providing access to state-of-the-art knowledge on technologies required useful for project delivery. The topics of these workshops are relevant to not only BioMedBridges partners, but to the wider biological community working at the interface of the data sciences.

3.2 Workshop 3 – Preparing for the data deluge

3.2.1 Workshop overview

This knowledge exchange workshop ran on 15-16 May 2014 in the EMBL-EBI South Building. The programme and course materials are available at – <http://www.biomedbridges.eu/trainings/knowledge-exchange-workshop-preparing-data-deluge>. The workshop was aimed at technical representatives from the BMS research infrastructures and their counterparts from the European e-infrastructures. It aimed to outline the data challenges facing the biological sciences and the data support required by both research infrastructures and their users.

The workshop combined presentations, discussions and breakout sessions that explored the scope of data use by RIs. The workshop began with a presentation from ELIXIR Technical Coordinator Rafael Jimenez that outlined

the growing ‘data deluge’ in the biological sciences. This talk explained the complex problem of computing, moving and storing the ever-increasing volumes of data that biology can now produce. A series of presentations followed covering different topics in the biological sciences – genomics, proteomics, imaging, metabolomics, clinical data – that outlined the data challenges in each area. Common themes across the RIs were identified during discussions. Participants from the e-infrastructures – EGI, EUDAT, GÉANT, PRACE – also provided short presentations that outlined the services they were able to provide, the mission they have to support European research, and how the BMS RIs can work with them to solve data issues. Alberto Di Meglio from CERN presented on the experiences of the high-energy physics community, and how the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) project drove innovation in compute, networking and storage.

Two invited speakers also presented use cases on current solutions for big data. The first speaker was Wolfgang Lengert from the European Space Agency (ESA) Earth Observation who talked about the data infrastructure required for a network of earth monitoring satellites. Arpad Szomoru from the Joint Institute for Very-long-baseline interferometry (VLBI) in Europe (JIVE) gave the second talk, focused on radio astronomy and the various international projects around the world that are currently collecting petabytes, and will soon be collecting exobytes, of raw data each year.

3.2.2 Workshop participants

A total of 29 people participated in the workshop; including representatives from BioMedBridges, eight ESFRI-BMS (EATRIS, ELIXIR [Sweden/UK nodes], EMBRC, ERINHA, EU-OPENSREEN, Euro-BioImaging, Instruct, ISBE), four e-infrastructures (DANTE, EGI, EUDAT, PRACE), and invited speakers from JIVE, ESA and CERN.

The participants represented a wide range of scientific disciplines, from the molecular life sciences to high-energy physics and radio astronomy. Despite the varied backgrounds, computing was a common theme that united all delegates. The sharing of knowledge and raising awareness of the different challenges each area faces in terms of dealing with very large data sets helped everyone to better understand what needs to be achieved in the future.

Figure 1 Participants' country of origin: Workshop 3 – Preparing for the data deluge

Figure 2 ESFRI 'bridges' built: Workshop 3 – Preparing for the data deluge

3.2.3 Documentation from the workshop

Speaker slides, materials and documents can be found on the workshop webpage:

<http://www.biomedbridges.eu/trainings/knowledge-exchange-workshop-preparing-data-deluge>

Outcomes of the workshop included the following:

- A list of common biological data challenges faced by the life sciences was collated
- Existing solutions to these challenges from e-infrastructures were identified
- Collaborative solutions were explored
- Proposals on how to action these solutions were made

During the workshop participants contributed to a shared 'living document'. This Google Doc allowed real-time note taking and documentation of presentations as they occurred. It helped organisers to capture comments, questions and answers that are normally not recorded during a workshop. Participants were also able to add notes and links to useful documentation, furthering the 'knowledge exchange' element of the workshop. These outcomes are expanded upon in the workshop report (see below).

BioMedBridges and representatives from the research infrastructures prepared a report following the workshop. The report summarises the findings of the workshop, outlines the current and future challenges of 'big data', and how coordination will be key to overcoming these problems as they arise. The report can be accessed via Zenodo¹.

3.2.4 Workshop feedback

The initial challenge for many participants was to be able to see outside the boundaries of their own disciplines. For those working as part of a research infrastructure, it meant realising that the e-infrastructures have existing solutions to their data problems. From the perspective of the e-infrastructures, they first needed to understand the actual problems faced by biologists in computational terms.

Both groups – and the spectrum of representatives in between – had to understand the challenges from both sides. In terms of data transfer, compute and storage, the challenges are quite often simple – more network cable, larger CPU farms, increased numbers of spinning drives – but this is not a simple

¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/13942#.VYQrKFVVhHx>

problem when applied to the biological sciences. One issue is the dispersed nature of biological data: there are thousands of sites across Europe generating, analysing, transferring and storing their own data and submitting it to centralised repositories. Whilst the volume of biological data is smaller, the infrastructure is more widely distributed when compared to physics or astronomy research. Technology is a main factor here, with high-throughput biological apparatus—genome sequencers, mass spectrometers and microscopes—being smaller and cheaper than instruments in other disciplines.

The workshop provided a useful forum for participants to learn more about how research infrastructures need to prepare for growing volumes of biological data. Verbal comments from those present suggest that similar meetings should be held in future; these would continue the forum for RIs to discuss data challenges, and to exchange knowledge with the e-infrastructures and others working in the area. Such meetings would also serve to drive collaborations between RIs and the e-infrastructures. As a result of this workshop, proposals were put together to run a follow-up workshop that would help research infrastructures in planning to deal with the biological data they will generate or become responsible for. This idea formed the basis of the fourth workshop – Data strategies for research infrastructures – that explored approaches to creating data strategy plans for RI and user data. The report from this workshop is presented below.

3.3 Workshop 4 – Data strategies for research infrastructures

3.3.1 Workshop overview

This knowledge exchange workshop ran on 19 February 2015 at the European Southern Observatory (ESO), Garching, Germany. The programme and course materials are available online². The workshop was aimed at project managers and coordinators of research infrastructures. It aimed to help the participants understand the importance of having a well defined data strategy for their research infrastructure, both in terms of managing internal data challenges and in terms of providing the data-related support required by infrastructure users.

The workshop combined presentations, discussions and breakout sessions to explore RI and user needs. The day began with presentations on the technical, scientific, financial and formal (political, legal, ethical, social) drivers that influence the development of a data strategy. These talks served to highlight the varied landscape the research infrastructures work in, each dealing with different scientific data and providing varied technical services to the life science community. Two use-case presentations provided examples of current data strategies. ESO astronomer Michael Sterzik presented on the approach ESO is taking with data from Earth-based telescopes. Martin Golebiewski, from the Heidelberg Institute for Theoretical Studies, presented the second use case on data strategies in distributed systems biology research.

Figure 3 Michael Sterzik from ESO presents

² <http://www.biomedbridges.eu/trainings/knowledge-exchange-workshop-data-strategies-research-infrastructures>

Two breakout sessions were also run during the workshop. The first focussed on understanding RI data requirements – what data the RI works with, missing knowledge, challenges and ways to prioritise data strategy. The second explored the current and future users of RI – identifying who they are, what they need and challenges in ensuring that these needs are met by the research infrastructures. These sessions provided a means for participants to discuss their RI, to explore data needs that they had perhaps not fully considered, to share knowledge and understanding and to outline successful approaches to planning data strategies.

3.3.2 Workshop participants

A total of 29 people participated in the workshop, including representatives from BioMedBridges, eight ESFRI-BMS (BBMRI, EATRIS, ELIXIR, Euro-Bioimaging, Infrafrontier, Instruct, ISBE, MIRRI). Two of the e-infrastructure were present (EGI, EUDAT, and the e-IRG reflection group); as well as representatives from the food and health research infrastructures (EuroDISH, dbNP), patient registries (PARENT) and a computational modelling network (Combine). The RIs represented a range of maturity levels with regards to data strategy planning and implementation. Several RIs already have fully developed strategies in place, and could offer their advice and experience; whilst others were less mature and came seeking information on how best to develop a data strategy for their community.

Figure 4 Participants' country of origin: Workshop 4 – Data strategies for research infrastructures

Figure 5 ESFRI 'bridges': Workshop 4 – Data strategies for research infrastructures

3.3.4 Documentation from the workshop

Speaker slides, materials and documents can be found on the workshop webpage³.

Outcomes of the workshop included the following:

- Participants gained a better understanding of data-related requirements for research infrastructures
- Understanding of how to support the data-related needs of RI users
- Important elements to include in a robust data strategy were defined
- Information on the support available for managing large-scale data was provided.

These outcomes will aid BMB partners and other research infrastructures in creating data strategies and devising long-term plans for data management. For some, the workshop helped to refine and expand existing strategies, ensuring that the steps they are taking are up to date and reflects the current data environment. For others, it provided a useful basis from which to work towards a data strategy for their infrastructure by combining the experiences of more advanced infrastructures with the particular needs of the individual research infrastructure and its users. These outcomes are further expanded upon in a white paper written after the workshop (see below).

Participants contributed to a shared 'living document' throughout the workshop. This Google Doc allowed real-time note taking and documentation of presentations as they occurred. It helped organisers to capture comments, questions and answers that are normally not recorded during a workshop. Participants were also able to add notes and links to useful documentation, furthering the 'knowledge exchange' element of the workshop.

³ <http://www.biomedbridges.eu/trainings/knowledge-exchange-workshop-data-strategies-research-infrastructures>

At the end of the meeting participants raised a number of key points:

- Research infrastructures need to drive a change in culture.
 - Firstly, to encourage scientists to feel responsible for their own data and ensure it is properly deposited and shared.
 - Secondly, to ensure data requirements are a central part of science funding and project development.
- Scientists at all levels need to be aware of the data requirements they will encounter in their work – training and outreach.
- Growth in data-intensive biological research requires urgent attention to establish best practice.

4 Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed: Yes No

5 Adjustments made

None

6 Background information

This deliverable relates to WP 12; background information on this WP as originally indicated in the description of work (DoW) is included below.

WP 12 Title: Training
 Lead: Cath Brooksbank (EMBL)
 Participants: EMBL

This work package will provide training on the tools and services developed within the BioMedBridges project.

Work package number	WP12	Start date or starting event:	month 1
Work package title	Training		
Activity Type	COORD		

Participant number	1:EMBL
Person-months per participant	42
<p>Objectives</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Deliver short courses to train project participants in relevant areas of bioinformatics that are outside of their current experience and necessary to build crosslinks between the data resources of the BMS RIs. 2. Produce documentation on the resources developed, for use initially within the project but ultimately by the end-users of the integrated services developed by BioMedBridges. 3. Deliver short courses enabling end-users of the biomedical research infrastructures to benefit from the developments of work packages 3–11. 	
<p>Task 1: Workshops for project participants and documentation of resources developed</p> <p>This task will deliver four workshops aimed at the BioMedBridges project participants during the first three years of the project, beginning towards the end of year 1. The topics of these workshops will be defined by the personnel working on each of the technical work packages, and coordinated by a full-time scientific training and outreach officer whose duties will be divided between this work package and WP2 (outreach). This individual will maintain an overview of the entire programme, work with the representatives from the technical work packages to develop the programmes for each workshop, ensure that the workshops are promoted effectively to relevant people within the project, and chair each workshop. The personnel working on the technical work packages will therefore need to dedicate a small but significant part of their time (estimated at two person months per work package throughout the project) to developing their workshop programmes and delivering training.</p> <p>Workshop topics</p> <p>Suggested topics include (but are not limited to) the following. This is likely to evolve, and workshop topics may merge or become further specialised as the project progresses.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practical solutions to interoperability standards development. This workshop will be led by WP3 (standards) and the main target audience will be WP4 (technical integration). The goal will be to enable those integrating the different BMS RI data sets to do so using an agreed set of standards and molecular identifiers defined by WP3. Input from the use cases will ensure that discussions and actions remain rooted in practical solutions to real data integration problems. The technology watch group will select trainers who can educate the delegates about any new developments 	

beyond BioMedBridges that might provide solutions to ongoing interoperability problems within the project.

- Practical solutions to secure data access. This workshop will be led by WP5 (Secure access) and the main target audience will be WP4 (technical integration). The goal of the workshop will be to enable those constructing the links between the BMS RIs' data sets to do so in a way that respects the rights of patients and healthy volunteers without impeding legitimate research. This workshop will include sessions led by experts on ethical and legal aspects of personal data sharing, and may involve representatives from patient groups.
- Practical solutions to development of web services. This will be led by WP4 (technical integration) and the main target audience will be the use cases (WPs 6–10). The goal will be to inform the development of programmatic access to integrated data sets spanning several BMS RIs and to develop workflows that reflect the needs of researchers using the BMS RIs. Input from the use cases will ensure that discussions and actions remain rooted in practical solutions to real data integration problems. The technology watch group will select trainers who can educate the delegates about any new web service or search technologies beyond BioMedBridges.
- Practical solutions to database development and interoperability. This will be led by WP4 (technical integration) and the target audience will be the use cases. The goal of the workshop will be to stimulate the development of integrated search tools spanning multiple BMS-RIs. This workshop will also include opportunities for the different use cases to learn from each other.

Workshops will be short and intensive (2–3 days), based on a combination of presentations, discussions, practical computer-based problem solving, and documentation writing. Each workshop will be hosted by a different BMS RI.

As these workshops are intended to define, and begin to action, a set of practical solutions, numbers of delegates will be kept small and that the ratio of trainers to delegates high – typically 5 trainers and 20 delegates in each workshop making 25 in total. Logistics and administrative support (registrations, inviting trainers, travel arrangements, answering delegates' queries, etc.) will be provided by the BioMedBridges Project manager with support from the EMBL-EBI's Outreach and Training Team. We will use events management systems and standard operating procedures that are already successfully running at the EMBL-EBI. The fact that we have considerable experience of running courses and workshops, and tried and tested systems for doing so, represents excellent added value for BioMedBridges.

Documentation

An outcome of each workshop will be the production of documentation to support the target audience of each workshop in implementing what they have learned. The trainers and trainees will take joint responsibility for writing clear guidelines for a specific topic. On the last day of each workshop, the delegates will define a set of frequently asked questions, and will work with the speakers/trainers to produce a clear set of answers. The BioMedBridges Scientific Training Officer will compile, edit and make this documentation available, initially to project members, and ultimately to end-users of the services developed by BioMedBridges. Members of personnel from the technical workpackages will take responsibility for

keeping this documentation up to date.

Task 2: Training for end-users of the BMS RIs.

In the fourth year of the project we will deliver training to end users of the integrated services developed by BioMedBridges. We will deliver two courses, which will be a combination of lectures, demos, discussions and hands-on computer-based tutorials. Personnel from the use cases will deliver these courses, and each course will be aimed at a different target audience – one focused on fundamental research, the other on translational and clinical research. By the end of year 3 of BioMedBridges, we anticipate that the individual BMS research infrastructures will be funded and are likely to be running training programmes for their own stakeholders. Using materials developed for the abovementioned courses, and our extensive network of training contacts developed through other initiatives such as the IMI Education and Training projects, we will also make the most of any opportunities to support these training programmes. We will also identify appropriate conferences at which we can offer training workshops.

7 Attachments

1. Workshop 3: <http://www.biomedbridges.eu/trainings/knowledge-exchange-workshop-preparing-data-deluge>
2. Workshop 4: <http://www.biomedbridges.eu/trainings/knowledge-exchange-workshop-data-strategies-research-infrastructures>